

Conference Abstract

The beginning of the dormouse monitoring program in Normandy, France (Poster presentation)

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Abstract

Bibliography can be used as a source of informations on the ecology and threats to the Hazel Dormouse. However, little data is available on French dormouse populations, and population trends remain unknown. The Hazel Dormouse is a protected species in France, but no particular attention is afforded to it by political policies. In 2018, the GMN (Groupe Mammalogique Normand) started a dormouse monitoring program in Normandy (France), based on volunteer work by its members. The aim of the program is to obtain information about local dormouse populations using nestbox monitoring at 10 study sites spread throughout Normandy, over a period of 5 to 10 years. The first years of the program were devoted to the search for potential study sites, the construction of nearly 400 nestboxes and their installation and monitoring at 8 study sites (beginning in 2019 for the first site). Since then, Hazel Dormouse nests and/or individuals have been observed in nestboxes at 7 study sites, with interannual fluctuations. The GMN is expanding its research to an additional two new sectors in 2022 or 2023. Further analysis will follow over the next few years.

Keywords

Hazel Dormouse, monitoring, Normandy

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